

INTEGRATION OF ARCHITECTURAL TERMS INTO THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article examines the integration of architectural terms into the Russian language. It explores how architectural vocabulary has been adopted and adapted within contemporary Russian, analyzing the linguistic and cultural factors that contribute to this phenomenon. The study delves into specific examples of architectural terminology, illustrating their origins, usage, and the processes through which they become embedded in the Russian lexicon.

Keywords: architectural terms, russian language, linguistic integration, cultural adaptation, globalization, language dynamics, lexical borrowing, terminology adaptation.

Architecture plays an important role in the life of societies, both ancient and modern: as the art of designing structures, it carries a symbolic meaning and reflects not only the cultural characteristics of a civilization of a certain era and the religious symbols of the people, but also the spiritual aspirations of its creators. With the accelerated development of modern science in the field of social and information space, scientific information is gaining key importance. Given the role of media as a medium for multiple discourses, it is possible to hypothesize the development of architectural discourse, which also acts as a reflection of a certain area of human knowledge [1].

Architectural discourse includes texts (scientific works on architecture, guidebooks, travel notes, works of art, etc.) and participants in this extensive discussion (architects, artists, critics, political and religious figures, journalists, thinkers, writers, etc.) in specific socio-historical contexts. The lexical composition of the special language of architecture is diverse. It includes three main blocks of terminology: general scientific, interdisciplinary and highly specialized.

Defining the boundaries between these blocks is not always straightforward. In scientific speech, which uses language to denote architectural activity, there is an interpenetration of highly specialized and general literary vocabulary. In the process of researching the material in foreign languages, the following structural types of architectural terms were identified: abaca, apse, prong, dropper, excedra, iconostasis, pendant, rosette, rotunda, sole.

This approach requires taking into account various types of knowledge (linguistic and extralinguistic factors, special and everyday concepts) and

phenomena such as measuring social knowledge horizontally and vertically, as well as taking into account scientific, professional, cultural and other parameters of the term. The terms used to connect different fields of knowledge play the role of special cognitive structures - frames. It is important to determine which concepts define the terminological nomination and serve to capture, store and transfer scientific knowledge.

L. S. Rudinskaya identifies several ways of forming terminology, including lexico-semantic, morphological, syntactic, as well as mixed methods. Polysemy, synonymy and antonymy are common linguistic processes in terminology. Morphological methods of forming terms include the use of affixes such as suffixes, prefixes, as well as methods of prefixation and suffixation. The syntactic method involves the creation of multicomponent nomination tools, such as term combinations. Borrowings can also be a potential source of terminology enrichment [4].

The various parts of the words are attached to the generating initial base in a fixed sequence. Architectural vocabulary is characterized by the absence of the formation of lexical nests due to the specific, material and, mainly, descriptive nature of architectural activity, where nouns predominate at the grammatical level. Since the content side of the terms cannot be observed directly, it becomes necessary to study them from the form side.

The units that make up the structure of the terminological nest (morpheme, word, syntagma, chain, paradigm, and others) explicitly or implicitly reflect all three main types of relations present in the internal structure of the language: syntagmatic, paradigmatic, and hierarchical. The structure of the terminological nest is formed from the interconnection of elements at both syntagmatic and paradigmatic levels. Syntagmatically, the nest is a set of word-formation chains, and the paradigmatic one is a set of term-forming paradigms [5].

Architectural vocabulary is characterized by the lack of formation of lexical nests due to the specific, material and, mainly, descriptive nature of architectural activity, where nouns predominate at the grammatical level [2]. Since the content side of the terms cannot be observed directly, it becomes necessary to study them from the form side. The study of the material structure of terms, which are means of scientific communication in a certain field of knowledge, creates conditions for understanding their semantic level.

For a complete picture, it is necessary to examine in more detail examples of prefix, suffix, prefix-suffix distribution of architectural terms - first of all

nouns, and second of all adjectives and participles recorded in architectural dictionaries. Adjectives and participles are studied, because, often, nouns are replaced in speech. The noun is very important, which, according to G. Mironova is a functional analogue of matter and is located at the top of the hierarchical structure of the system of parts of speech, since matter is the focus of properties and is able to create complex wholes [4].

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that architectural borrowings in modern Russian are not only an integral part of its development, but also reflect a variety of cultural influences and historical contexts. This process enriches the language, giving it new shades and opportunities for expressing thoughts and ideas. In addition, the use of architectural terms in various fields of activity contributes to the formation of general cultural literacy and the expansion of the linguistic arsenal of speakers. Thus, the study and conscious use of architectural borrowings not only contributes to the development of linguistic competence, but also broadens horizons and cultural understanding..

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